

COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND TERTIARY EDUCATION IN NIGERIA: IMPACTS, CHALLENGES AND WAY FORWARD

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Abstract

This conceptual paper examined the COVID-19 and its impacts, challenges and way forward in tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Indeed, the index case of Covid-19 was first reported in Wuhan-China at the end of 2019. The dreaded disease spread to almost all countries and territories in the world. In Nigeria, government underrated the outbreak of COVID-19 in various cities and villages thus undermining the implementation of initial precautionary measures which would have saved huge expenses while protecting the Nigerians from undue exposure to the virus. In tertiary level of education, the threat posed by COVID-19 in particular was compounded owing to its susceptibility to other impending challenges of poverty, poor health system, insurgencies, kidnapping, banditry, high population density, in addition to underlying educational challenges that have kept the country behind in equipping young people with resource development, impact and challenges of COVID-19 on tertiary education were also discussed. It was therefore recommended that government and concerned education stakeholders should ensure there are futuristic plans against similar experience.

Keywords: COVID-19, challenges, impact, pandemic, Tertiary Education

Introduction

The COVID-19 which was first reported in Wuhan-China at the end of 2019 has spread to almost all countries and territories in the world (Ozdemir, 2020). The forecast of its consequences, especially due to poor management of the spread by citizens and government at all levels, has been problematic for all sectors (Mofijur Et al. 2021; Yahaya, 2021). World Health Organisation (2020) sees Corona virus as highly infectious disease that has plagued the world, thus, on the 30th of January 2019 (WHO) declared CoVID-19 as a public health emergency of international concern". Since then, it has spread to over 223 countries and has affected over 240 million persons globally. An estimation of 5 million deaths in the world and 2,500 in Nigeria from over 200 thousand persons infected respectively (Hansen et al., 2021 Hou et al., 2020 Tria et al., 2020 Yamin., 2020 Yahaya., 2021). That is to say, that the disease is characterised by high mobility and mortality rate alongside other ailments.

In Nigeria, the emergence of COVID-19 was indeed an explosion across the states. The threat posed to education sector in particular according to Abideen (2020) was compounded owing to its susceptibility in addition to poverty, poor health system, insurgencies, kidnapping banditry, high population density etc. These in addition to underlying educational challenges that have kept the country behind in equipping young people with resource development, the COVID-19 pandemic further worsen the situation.

At the climax of the pandemic precisely on April 21st, 2020, about 1.72 billion learners have been affected with the abrupt shutting down of schools in reaction to the COVID-19 pandemic (Samuel, 2020). According to United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation monitoring in the period under review, 191 countries have implemented nationwide closures and five have implemented local closures, impacting negatively on about 98.4 percent of the world's student population (UNESCO, 2020). However, Nigeria was reported to have the high proportion of out-of-school children globally before COVID-19. For those that were enrolled, there was devastating evidence that learning levels were much lower than expected suggesting a continued halt in learning for children (Azevedo, Hasan, Goldemberg, Geven & Iqbal, 2021). Indeed, many unified National examinations were suspended. With all the measures above Nigeria and fifty four other African countries are at the present with confirmed cases of COVID-19 and death toll increased tremendously. This led to closure of borders and banned on international flights, with local and international trade declined at geometric rate (Zambakari, Lipsitch, Ioannidis, Fuller, Fuller, Hansohm, & Gormley, 2020).

However, the exact impact and challenges of covid-19 on Education sector may be difficult because of poor data base, public and private institutions in remote areas and attitude or believe of the people about COVID-19. The challenges facing rural primary schools are very different from those facing urban universities; the challenges facing urban and rural secondary schools are different too (Du Plessis & Mestry, 2019; Şahin, 2020). Thus, the impact varies as the case may be. Therefore, this study seek to look at the impact, challenges and way forward to contain Covid-19 among tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria.

Concept of Covid-19 Pandemic

Corona virus (CoVs) is a family of virus which caused respiratory and intestinal illnesses in humans and animals (Cui, Shi, 2019). According to Abd El-Aziz & Stockand (2020) Corona virus generally caused mild colds in victim. However, the emergence of the severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) epidemic in China and the Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) show that they can also cause severe disease. As present, "the COVID-19" which the world is currently battling with is responsible for the recent outbreak of coronavirus disease (Chakraborty & Maity, 2020). The symptoms of most patients with COVID-19 represent moderately calm cases. Recent studies (Davis, Assaf, GMcCorkell, *et al*, 2021 and Guo, Radloff, Wawrzynsk & Cloyes, 2020) have shown that quite a number of patients with covid-19 experienced fever and dry cough, while some also had shortness of breath, fatigue, and other typical symptoms, such as muscle pain, confusion, headache, sore throat, diarrhea, and vomiting.

The best way to prevent and slow down transmission is to be well informed about the disease and how the virus spreads. Protect yourself and others from infection by staying at least 1 metre apart from others, wearing a properly fitted mask, and washing your hands or using an alcohol-based rub frequently. Get vaccinated when it's your turn and follow local guidance.

The virus can spread from an infected person's mouth or nose in small liquid particles when they cough, sneeze, speak, sing or breathe. These particles range from larger respiratory droplets to smaller aerosols. It is important to practice respiratory etiquette, for

example by coughing into a flexed elbow, and to stay home and self-isolate until you recover if you feel unwell.

Nigeria Tertiary Education and COVID-19 Pandemic

Tertiary Education as stipulated in the national policy on education (2013) is the education given after Post Basic Education institutions such as Universities, Colleges of Education, Monotechnics, Polytechnics and other specialized institutions. The need for these institutions is rapidly increasing at geometrical rate; and this has therefore brought about the rise in student/lecturer ratio (Azi, 2019, Channy & Ogunniran, 2019 and Uhumwuangh & Diakpomrere, 2019). The increase has consequently compounded management of students against possible outbreak of pandemic such as COVID-19.

Undeniably before the outbreak of COVID-19 epidemic diseases such as Lassa fever, bird flu, monkey pox, Ebola disease and others were experienced in Nigeria and of course didn't weigh down the socio-economic and educational system like that of COVID-19. Hence, predicted effect of COVID-19 has continued to raise dust in the country educational system, knowing well the possible effects of the prolong damages it may cause (Okonkwo, 2021).

In a precautionary move intended however at preventing the spread of the coronavirus (Covid-19) disease in the country, the Federal Ministry of Education on March 27th, 2020 ordered the immediate closure of all educational institutions nationwide. Other measures taken includes flight restrictions on some high-risk countries, restrictions of public gatherings like churches and mosques, suspension of sporting events, shut down of schools in some states, suspension of orientation and other activities by National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) all to forestall further spread of the virus. But unlike other countries where governments immediately came up with policy measures to fill the gap created by school closure; the Nigerian government had no clear-cut plans to keep students engaged in academic activities (Yahaya, 2021). In response to the COVID-19 hit, different state colleges and universities particularly private institutions of higher learning came up with internet-based learning. Conversely, despite internet base learning the gap created by school closure was not filled because of unstable power, inefficiency of internet facilities and the low purchasing power of the parents in the country (Dutta, 2020 Olatunde, *et al.*, 2021). This had serious long impact on the education sector in most countries.

Impacts on Tertiary Education

As the COVID-19 Pandemic has revolutionized digital world and indeed online education, Tertiary Education students with skills to undertake internet-based learning faced poor internet infrastructure and lack of electricity supply (Zhong, 2020). Consequently, learning remotely was not feasible in most Nigeria communities. Undeniably, COVID-19 pandemic laid bare the wretchedness of not only tertiary education but the entire education system in Nigeria. The outbreak of covid-19 according to Yahaya (2021) has clearly revealed that there is digital divide between an average Nigerian student and his counterparts in most developing and developed world. The system obviously lacks the capacity to migrate universities and colleges to virtual learning platform.

The COVID-19 Pandemic has also justified the demand of Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASSU) for overhauling of Nigerian Tertiary institutions as institutions in the country lack the capacity to compete with their counterpart Universities in the world in terms of technological advancement and meeting up with 21st reality of education (Iju and Musa, 2021). In addition, during the lockdown, the facilities in most institutions were underutilized which may as a result of not been used for a long period of time. There is no assurance that all the learners who left the school will be back in school after the pandemic lockdown; some may have changed their minds in going to school as a waste of time. Some on the other hand may have joined bad groups shifting their attention away from school and some may have died during the period under review. The effect of all these according to Samuel (2020) may not be easily noticed now; the future of the learners in this category is therefore naturally exposed to a serious academic crash if there are no proper interventions.

Impacts on Funding of Tertiary Education

The unexpected disruption of the education system in Nigeria as a result of the pandemic has generally led to changes in the plans towards financing the education of children and the education system at large (Kaden, 2020). The abrupt change in school calendar which led to extension of semester resulted in extra payments of school fees. During the lockdown some parents were forced to procure laptops, android phones including data, television cables and other means of ICT, this is to ensure their wards move with the new innovative of the online classes at various levels designed for teachers to reach out to their students. Most of the developing universities in Nigeria could not afford the payment of their lecturers during the period of lockdown because students are not in school, some have not paid the school levies before the emergence of the pandemic leading to school proprietors not having access to inflow of income to welfare their lecturers working in their respective universities, in fact there is fear of whether some private universities in Nigeria will be able to survive and keep existing after the pandemic lockdown. Even when there is a standing order that says no work no pay in Nigeria, during the lockdown the governments at some levels still ensured continuous payments of staff in schools, ministries of education knowing well that they are not working for their earnings during the lockdown. There is no doubt that the expenses run as workers payment during the period of lockdown are mere gifts and not payment for work done, this will surely have effect on the future educational finance because the working time does not tallies with the staffs payment. The sad truth about this development is if it persists, it may have serious impacts on the commitment of governments towards the education system in the face of competing demands from the healthcare, business and other sectors serving vulnerable segments of the society at large.

Impact on Graduates and School Leavers

There is no doubt that students in final classes in lower and higher levels of education system of Nigeria has been held on a spot; they were unable to graduate or even move to the next level in their academic pursuit this has led to a great set back of the smooth running of educational sector of Nigeria and the world at large. The career of university graduates was severely affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. They experienced teaching interruptions in the final part of their studies, interruptions in their assessments, and finally they are likely to graduate at the beginning of a major global recession, because

there is no doubt there will be global recession in the economy of the world at large at the end of the pandemic lockdown.

The Challenges of COVID-19 on Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

The sudden outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has technically not only exposed the deteriorating state of infrastructure and facilities in all sector of Nigeria but also depicts the state of dilapidation of the tertiary education in Nigeria (Adebayo, Oduntan, Fasola & Adebisi, 2021). In reality, apart from health sector, no other area has been heated by COVID-19 like education (Yahaya, 2021).

The major challenge in tertiary education is in the area of digital transformation in teaching and learning process. Quite a number of lecturers and students in institution of higher learning without reliable internet access will struggle to participate in digital learning. This gap is seen across countries and between income brackets within countries. In Nigeria for instance, the challenge of transforming to online teaching and learning environment will pose a grave consequence as both lecturers and students are handicapped.

Way Forward

Training of lecturers and students on ICT

Lecturers and students need to be trained on ICT and e-learning facilities as how they can be used to support learning. In-service teachers as well as the pre-service teachers in educational institutions should be well trained in blended teaching methods. They equally need to be equipped with ICT gadgets and as such learning can take place irrespective of time and distance.

Subsidising e-Learning Platform

Provision of computer and mobile data packages telecommunication subsidies to all lecturers as well as students from low-income households. Government can also provide supports such as solar-powered educational devices, pre-loaded with offline academic resources to students from disadvantage and vulnerable communities to cushion the effects of the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on education.

Conclusion

The outbreak of corona virus has shaken the educational sector of Nigeria off its strength. In fact, looking at the trend of the pandemic, it could be something we are going to live with for a long period of time. The pandemic has led to the shortage of funds in the educational system, parents as well are being faced with the reality of having to pay extra cost on their children academics whenever they resume school. The outbreak of the corona virus coupled with the lockdown of schools at various levels of education in Nigeria had served as test for the education technology interventions for teaching-learning activities. The covid-19 pandemic creates exceptional challenges on the government, students, and parents that have emphasized and could amplify some of the loopholes in the system.

Suggestions

Since it was observed that there were no proper plans in place to curb and manage the influence of corona virus on the educational system, it is highly recommended that:

- i. Government and concerned educational personnel should ensure there are futuristic plans in case of another similar experience as nobody knows when other occurrences may happen in future. Thus plans are to be made in ensuring that the future of the education system is secured. In addition, having observed that even the E-Learning chosen as the alternatives to be used in reaching out to the learners in the period of lockdown has not successfully work because of non-employment of expert to manage the ICT section of the Nigeria Education system, huge tariff charges from various network providers in Nigeria.
- ii. Nigeria Ministry of Education to employ experts in the area of ICT to further introduce programs that will enhance the productivity of the education sector in order to compete with the outside world even in the period of global pandemic lockdown. All these will still maintain the social distancing rules, helps the teacher to teach, reach out to learners through voice, written words or even video conversations. Learners won't have to miss a lot as a result of not physically present in class.

Also, if after a period of time, the move to reopen schools for learners in terminal classes works perfectly, it can also be extended to other levels of education enforcing that all related health rules and regulations are been followed to details in order to ensure much damage is not done to the development of the Nigerian educational sector.

- iii. Teachers and tertiary institutions staffs are to soft-pedal their actions with the government on the reopening of schools, they can as well volunteer to make provision for the preventive kits in schools and other related health facilities to curb the further spread of coronavirus in our schools, the Parent Teachers Association, Alumni, Schools Board of Governors.etc...are advised to extend more supportive hands in upholding the education sector of Nigeria. The future of the country's educational system is in the hands of everyone of us and we can't afford to allow it to be soiled with the interference of the coronavirus, private sectors and concerned individuals should as well come in to rescue the it from the impending doom which may spring up after the lockdown caused by covid-19 pandemic.

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